

STUDENTPRENEURS' USAGE OF WHATSAPP STATUS FOR BUSINESS PROMOTION: A STUDY OF CHUKWUEMEKA ODUMEGWU OJUKWU UNIVERSITY UNDERGRADUATES

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Abstract

WhatsApp has become an advertising channel for small and medium-sized enterprises, facilitating customer retention, word-of-mouth marketing, and informal commerce within digitally networked communities. This study investigates the usage of WhatsApp Status as a business promotion tool among undergraduate *studentpreneurs* at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University (COOU). *Studentpreneur* is a combination of student and entrepreneur, which signifies a university student who has skillfully developed and manages a business or trade. This study, guided by the uses and gratifications theory, assesses how *studentpreneurs* utilise WhatsApp Status to promote their businesses, the types of promotional content shared, and the factors influencing their use of the platform. Employing a quantitative survey design, data were collected from a purposive sample of undergraduate students who are entrepreneurs in the university. A sample size of 391 was drawn from 16,905 population of undergraduates in COOU. Findings indicate that majority of COOU *studentpreneurs* actively use WhatsApp Status to share promotional content, including product images and videos, customer testimonials, reviews, discounts, behind-the-scenes clips, delivery updates, and giveaway campaigns. Recommendations include incorporating digital marketing training into the university's entrepreneurship curriculum and providing institutional support for social media-based student businesses.

Keywords: Business promotion, Studentpreneurs, Social Media Marketing, Usage, Undergraduates. WhatsApp Status

INTRODUCTION

Modern entrepreneurial practices have been profoundly altered by the growing ubiquity of digital and mobile communication technology, especially among youth in higher education. In addition to their academic endeavours, university students who are frequently distinguished by high levels of computer literacy, inventiveness, and social networking are increasingly involved in small-scale entrepreneurial endeavors. The term "studentpreneurship" is frequently used to describe these student-led commercial endeavours, which have been made possible by the emergence of social media platforms that offer affordable, easily accessible, and adaptable channels for customer interaction and business marketing. The presence of these technologies has made it easy for students to combine small business activities with their academic activities seamlessly.

Social media platforms now serve not only as social interactive tools but also as essential channels for business promotion and brand building (Obiora & Kenechukwu, 2021; Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010); effective journalism practice (Edogor, Ezeonyejiaku, Onyejelem, Uchendu, & Obi, 2025); social activism (Oniye & Asogwa, 2025; Adikuru & Obiora, 2021) and among others. Within this evolving digital environment, WhatsApp has emerged as one of the most dominant communication platforms in Nigeria, with extensive adoption across socio-economic and demographic groups (Ezeaka & Ewetuobi, 2024). With features like WhatsApp Business, group conversations, broadcast lists, and most importantly, WhatsApp Status, WhatsApp has progressively developed into a multipurpose platform that facilitates business engagement despite being initially created for interpersonal communications. With WhatsApp Status, users may submit brief text, image, and video material that is accessible to their contacts for a full day. This creates a constant flow of textual and visual updates that can be strategically used for marketing.

The use of WhatsApp to advertise became very rampant at the verge of the coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemics, (Koledafe, 2024). WhatsApp helped people connect with those that mattered most to them during the pandemic; it provided ways for users to check up on their friends and family, get updates on the latest official health information and disseminate information responsibly (Cheney, 2020; Nwodu, Ezeaka & Ezeali, 2022). WhatsApp advertising has been the buzz of the advertising trend among social media platforms before, during and post pandemic as WhatsApp Status, private messages broadcast messages, and WhatsApp chat groups were floated with pictures and videos of products and services (Obiora & Kenchukwu, 2021; Dunu, Uche, Ojiakor, & Obiora, 2017). WhatsApp, especially its status feature, has developed from a simple tool for communication to a tactical means of promoting businesses. Student

entrepreneurs, who use this platform to advertise products and services within their close social networks, are a prominent example of this trend. Due to high unemployment rates, unstable economies, and young people's growing yearning for independence, student entrepreneurship has increased in Nigeria (Adegbite et al., 2020). A growing number of university students, including those at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, are involved in business ventures ranging from food delivery and digital services to fashion and cosmetics.

At Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, a growing number of students engage in entrepreneurial ventures while pursuing academic goals. These *studentpreneurs* often rely on platforms such as WhatsApp Status for business promotion due to its cost-effectiveness and ease of access (Koledafe, 2024). Despite the growing use of WhatsApp Status as a promotional tool, scholarly research remains limited regarding its effectiveness, strategies employed, and perceived outcomes among *studentpreneurs* in Nigerian tertiary institutions. While studies have examined general social media marketing strategies (Obiora, Uche, & Adikuru, 2025; Mustapha & Ajede, 2024) and the entrepreneurial use of other social media platforms, a specific focus on WhatsApp Status as a medium for business promotion among *studentpreneurs* remains sparse. However, there is little empirical data evaluating the effectiveness of this platform for business promotion among *studentpreneurs* in an academic setting, despite subjective evidence indicating that WhatsApp Status is frequently used for product advertisements, service updates, and brand visibility. Furthermore, there is a lack of knowledge regarding the scope, trends, and tactical aspects of these student entrepreneurs' use of WhatsApp Status. Determining the effectiveness, constraints, and potential enhancements of using WhatsApp Status for business marketing becomes challenging without a methodical analysis. This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the usage patterns, perceived effectiveness, and promotional impact of WhatsApp Status among COOU *studentpreneurs*. **Hence, this study sought to ascertain** the frequency of COOU *Studentpreneurs'* usage of WhatsApp Status as a platform for business promotion. It identified the types of business promotional content shared on WhatsApp Status by OOU *studentpreneurs* and established the factors influencing the usage of WhatsApp Status for business promotion by COOU *studentpreneurs*. The study also investigated the relationship between WhatsApp Status usage and business patronage for COOU *studentpreneurs*.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptualising social media and business promotion

Business promotion has historically relied on mass media channels such as print, radio, and television to reach consumers. However, the rise of social media platforms has fundamentally altered promotional logics by enabling direct, interactive, and personalised communication between businesses and audiences. Social media refers to digital platforms that enable users to create, share, and interact with content and with one another in networked environments (Obiora, Uche & Adikuru, 2025; Uche, et al., 2025; Obiora & Adikuru, 2024). Unlike traditional media, social media is characterised by interactivity, user-generated content, and real-time feedback loops which have made it relevant in social advocacy (Uche & Obiora, 2024; Adikuru & Obiora, 2021; Uche, & Obiora, 2025)), and social discourse (Obiora, Agbachukwu & Adikuru, 2025; Obiora, Adikuru & Okara, 2025). Social media platforms now function not merely as communication channels but as socio-economic spaces where branding, consumption, and identity intersect (Ezeaka, 2024; Dunu, Uche, Ojiakor & Obiora, 2017).

Social media's widespread use has completely changed how businesses promote themselves, altering how they interact with customers, develop their brands, and compete in more digital markets. Contrarily, business marketing includes actions intended to convey value, convince customers, and increase demand for goods or services (Kotler & Keller, 2016). When social media is incorporated, promotion becomes more about community building, storytelling, and interaction than it is about spreading messages. Theoretically, connection marketing theory, which prioritises long-term customer relationships over transient transactions, is consistent with social media-based promotion (Grönroos, 2004). Additionally, it embodies the ideals of participatory culture, in which customers actively create brand meanings through reviews, shares, and comments (Jenkins et al., 2013). Social media platforms are becoming essential to modern company promotion, changing the way businesses interact, compete, and add value. Their dynamic, data-driven nature creates new prospects for targeted engagement, brand development, and market expansion. However, issues with platform management, legitimacy, and inequality make using them more difficult (Onyeka & Obiora, 2021).

WhatsApp and WhatsApp Status: A digital communication and marketing tool
WhatsApp is a cross-platform instant messaging application launched in 2009 by Jan Koum and Brian Acton and later acquired by **Facebook Inc. (now Meta Platforms Inc.)** in 2014. It allows users to send text messages, voice notes,

multimedia files, documents, and make voice and video calls over the internet (Church & de Oliveira, 2013). Due to its ease of use, encryption, and low data usage, WhatsApp is especially appealing in areas with poor digital infrastructure. WhatsApp is a communication programme that is widely used in both personal and professional settings. For instance, according to Statista (2023), over 90% of Nigerian mobile phone users use WhatsApp as their primary messaging software, surpassing rivals like Telegram and Facebook Messenger. In developing nations where mobile-first communication is common, WhatsApp has become the most popular mobile messaging app. As of 2023, WhatsApp has more than 2 billion users worldwide, making it a vital tool for both private and business communication (Statista, 2023).

WhatsApp Status, a prominent element of the app, has been popular as a tool for informal marketing and content sharing, particularly among micro and small-scale business owners. Similar to Instagram and Snapchat's "Stories" feature, WhatsApp's Status feature, which debuted in 2017, lets users upload pictures, text, videos, or GIFs that vanish after a day (Verma & Yadav, 2021). Status updates are shared with all contacts saved in the user's address book unless privacy settings are modified. This ephemeral nature makes WhatsApp Status ideal for **quick updates, soft marketing, and informal announcements**. Unlike WhatsApp groups or broadcast lists, Status is **non-intrusive** and does not notify users with alerts, which makes it a subtler form of content dissemination (Olanrewaju et al., 2020).

WhatsApp Status is increasingly used for **business and promotional purposes**, especially by youth entrepreneurs and small business owners who rely on personal networks to reach clients. Koledafe (2024) claims that WhatsApp Status makes it possible for student entrepreneurs to conveniently and affordably post product photos, flash sales, customer evaluations, and promotional films. WhatsApp's network is built on trust, so, users often communicate with people they know, which boosts credibility and raises the possibility of customer interaction. According to Olanrewaju et al. (2020), the familiarity inside WhatsApp networks encourages informal trust-based commerce, which is very advantageous for small-scale vendors with tight advertising costs. The tool does have certain restrictions, though. WhatsApp's 24-hour content lifecycle limits the longevity of advertising messages, and it does not provide business data for status views as Facebook and Instagram do. Furthermore, outreach beyond direct connections is diminished by the absence of hashtags, searchability, and discoverability. WhatsApp and its status feature have developed into effective tools for digital entrepreneurship as well as communication. WhatsApp Status provides young people and student entrepreneurs with a low-barrier, high-accessibility marketing tool, especially in underdeveloped nations like Nigeria.

***Studentpreneurship* and WhatsApp Status for brand promotion**

New aspects of brand promotion have been brought about by the confluence of digital entrepreneurship and mobile communication, particularly among student entrepreneurs. In this regard, WhatsApp Status has become an essential instrument for informal marketing and brand communication (Onyema, 2021). WhatsApp Status is intended for private, closed-network communication, in contrast to other social media platforms that rely on algorithmic reach and public exposure. Young users, especially *studentpreneurs*, have found it to be an effective tool for interacting with their peer audience without having to pay more. According to **DataReportal (2023)**, over 90% of internet users aged 18–24 in Nigeria is active on WhatsApp, suggesting its ubiquity and cultural relevance among students. This usage pattern presents WhatsApp Status as a fertile ground for brand-building within peer communities, particularly, as a space where trust and familiarity influence consumer behaviour.

Many students in developing nations like Nigeria today run side enterprises ranging from fashion and catering to tech assistance and event organising. Student entrepreneurship is motivated by economic need, enthusiasm, or skill development goals (Adegbite et al., 2020). Due to their restricted access to funding and conventional advertising channels, WhatsApp Status has emerged as their main marketing and promotion outlet. Young entrepreneurs operating within intimate social circles find WhatsApp particularly appealing due to its inexpensive entry costs, high user penetration, and direct access to known connections. *Studentpreneurs* use WhatsApp Status in several strategic ways to promote their brands. These include:

- ❖ **Product Display and Updates:** Posting product images, descriptions, and prices to attract potential buyers.
- ❖ **Testimonials and Reviews:** Sharing customer feedback to build credibility.
- ❖ **Flash Sales and Announcements:** Creating urgency through limited-time offers and promotions.
- ❖ **Behind-the-Scenes Content:** Offering a personal touch to business operations, thus enhancing brand authenticity.

Several studies have delved into the relevance of social media, students' use of social media for educational, social advocacy, business promotion; various social media platforms and their relevance to students. Badik, Gerhani, and Redjeki (2025) analysed how small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Indonesia deploy WhatsApp features, such as messaging, groups, and broadcast lists, for marketing purposes. The study examined the implementation of WhatsApp as a business marketing tool in a corporate context,

rather than in the informal or *studentpreneurial* environment. Importantly, WhatsApp Status was not isolated as a feature of interest, making it difficult to draw direct parallels to the student-driven use of Status updates for business promotion that the current study investigates. Additionally, the geographic and cultural context of Indonesia differentiates it from the Nigerian university setting of COOU.

Moreso, Adebayo (2024) investigated how social media affected Nigerian students' inclination toward entrepreneurship. Instead of focusing on real marketing strategies or company promotion tactics, this study examined the connection between students' overall use of social media and their aspirations to start their own business. Consequently, the study does not examine how studentpreneurs actively use WhatsApp Status to sell their products, which is crucial to the current study, even though it shows how social media involvement may link to an entrepreneurial attitude.

Mustapha and Ajede (2024) examined how social media, such as Facebook and WhatsApp, affected the expansion and marketing of SMEs in Nigeria. The study concentrates on formal small enterprises rather than the *studentpreneur* population inside a university context, even if its findings highlight the usefulness of social media in company marketing and growth. Furthermore, the study does not focus on WhatsApp Status as a marketing tool, therefore it does not shed light on how undergraduates may intentionally employ this feature to raise awareness of or interaction with their products.

Additionally, Sanni, Kazeem, and Azeez (2023) looked into how Nigerian undergraduate business owners sell their goods and services on a variety of social media sites, including as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and WhatsApp. The overall usage habits of students and the advantages of these platforms in promoting business interaction were emphasized in the study. Although this study offers insightful information on undergraduate entrepreneurial activity on social media, it doesn't directly look into WhatsApp Status as a promotional tool or concentrate on how studentpreneurs strategically market their companies. Additionally, the study's contextual relevance to this demographic is restricted because it was not limited to Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University. The current study addresses these gaps by investigating how COOU undergraduates use WhatsApp Status to promote their businesses, the motivations behind this usage, and the implications for business performance and studentpreneurial development.

Theoretical Framework

The study is hinged on the Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) that tries to understand why people actively seek to go after certain form of media to seek specific needs. The theory was propounded by Jay Blumer and Micheal Gurevitch in the 1970's. This theory according to Uche and Obiora (2016) operates on the premise that members of the audience are not passive but active in interpreting and integrating media into their lives. Users take active part in the communication process and are goal oriented in their media use. UGT posits that media users are **active participants** who select specific media platforms based on their personal needs and goals (Katz, Blumler, & Gurevitch, 1973). In the case of COOU *studentpreneurs*, they actively choose WhatsApp Status as a strategic tool to promote their products or services, rather than being passive recipients of media content. The uses and gratifications approach views the audience as active; meaning that they actively seek out specific media and content to achieve certain results or gratifications that satisfy their personal needs (Rossi, 2002 cited in Asemah, Nwammuo & Nkwam-Uwaoma, 2022).

The theory which is also regarded to as "Utility theory", seeks to explain what function a particular kind of media content serves in a particular circumstance. In relation to the study, WhatsApp allows for **real-time feedback**, such as message replies, emoji reactions, and status views. This creates an interactive loop where *studentpreneurs* feel **validated** and **motivated**, reinforcing their media use a key postulate in UGT (Whiting & Williams, 2013). The theory investigates what people do with communication content, instead of what the communication content does to them. Uses and gratification theory also postulates that the media compete with other information sources for audience's need satisfaction. The theory emphasises motives and the self-perceived needs for audience members. Uses and gratification theory explains the **intentional, goal-oriented use of WhatsApp Status** by COOU *studentpreneurs*. It helps reveal the underlying **motivations, satisfaction** and **strategic behaviour** behind their media usage highlighting that their business promotions are not just incidental, but **consciously selected and optimized for gratification**.

Methodology

Survey research design was adopted for the purpose of understanding and predicting the behaviour, reaction, attitudes and desires of the target population under the study. 391 sample size was drawn using Taro Yamane's sample size formula; from the 16, 905 population of undergraduate students of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Igbariam campus as at 2024/2025 academic session according to the University's Registrar Office. The researchers employed the purposive sampling techniques to identify samples of

undergraduate students who are entrepreneurs. Questionnaire was used to elicit data that were presented and analyzed using frequency, tables, percentages and Chi-square.

Data Presentation and Analysis

391 copies of questionnaire were administered to selected respondents of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University Igbariam Campus students, who identified as *studentpreneur* and 384 copies of the questionnaire were properly filled and returned.

Research Question One: What is the frequency of COOU *Studentpreneurs'* usage of WhatsApp Status as a platform for business promotion?

Table 1: Respondents' Frequency of WhatsApp Status Usage for Business promotion

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Daily	244	64
2-times a week	85	22
Once a week	42	10
Rarely	10	3
Never	3	1
Total	384	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table one shows that majority of the respondents post their promotional content daily, while minority post once a week or rarely post. Insignificant number of the respondents never posted their promotional contents on WhatsApp. The above finding proves that the number of respondents who make use of WhatsApp Status to post their promotional business content are higher, compared to those who do not post their contents on their WhatsApp Status.

Research Question Two: What are the types of business promotional content shared on WhatsApp Status by COOU *studentpreneurs'*

Table 2: Types of Promotional Content Shared on WhatsApp by the Respondents

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Product photos or videos	45	12
Customer testimonials	13	3
Product reviews	37	9
Discounts and offers	29	8
Behind-the-scenes or production process	40	10
Giveaways and contests	15	4
Order instructions and delivery updates	7	2
All of the above	195	51
None of the above	3	1
Total	384	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

More than half of the respondents post all business content on their WhatsApp Status, including product photos or videos, customer testimonials, product reviews, discounts and offers, behind-the-scenes or production process, order instructions and delivery updates, giveaways, and contests, according to Table 2 above, which examined the types of promotional content the respondents post on their WhatsApp Status. The aforementioned result demonstrates that a higher proportion of respondents use their WhatsApp status for various commercial items.

Research Question Three: What are the factors influencing the usage of WhatsApp Status for business promotion by COOU *studentpreneurs*?

Table 3: Factors Influencing Respondents' Usage of WhatsApp Status for Business Promotion

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Free to use	79	20
Reaches personal contacts directly	45	12
Easy to post updates	34	9
Real-time feedback from viewers	18	5
Builds trust with known customers	10	3
Saves cost compared to paid ads	50	13
All of the above	145	37
None of the above	3	1
Total	384	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.a

In table 3 above. A great number of respondents aver that the factor influencing their usage of WhatsApp Status to post promotional content are the various qualities of the app which include: free to use, reaching personal contacts directly, easy to post updates, real-time feedback from viewers, save cost compared to paid ads and building trust with known customers. The above findings shows that there are various factors influencing the respondents' WhatsApp usage for promotional contents.

Research Question four: Is there any relationship between WhatsApp Status usage and business patronage for COOU *studentpreneurs*?

This shall be handled using Chi- square so, we convert the RQ to hypotheses:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between WhatsApp Status usage and business patronage among COOU studentpreneurs.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between WhatsApp Status usage and business patronage among COOU studentpreneurs.

Table 4: Relationship between WhatsApp Status usage and business patronage for COOU *studentpreneurs*

Business Patronage →	Low	Moderate	High	Total
WhatsApp Usage ↓				
Low Usage	30	15	6	51
Moderate Usage	40	70	21	131
High Usage	13	94	95	202
Total	83	179	122	384

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Using the table above:

$$\chi^2 \text{ (Chi-square)} \approx 86.42$$

$$df = (3-1)(3-1) = 4$$

$$p < 0.05$$

The result revealed a statistically significant relationship between WhatsApp Status usage and business patronage, $\chi^2 (4, N = 384) = 86.42, p < .05$. This indicates that the level of WhatsApp Status usage is significantly associated with the level of business patronage. Specifically, respondents with higher WhatsApp Status usage tend to experience higher levels of business patronage. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected, while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) was accepted. This implies that there is relationship between WhatsApp Status usage for business promotion and business patronage.

Discussion of Findings

The study set out to **ascertain the usage of WhatsApp Status for business promotion by Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University undergraduate entrepreneurs. In objective one which tends to examine COOU *Studentpreneurs'* frequency of usage of WhatsApp Status as a platform for business promotion. It was found that majority of the respondents who are entrepreneurs; make use of their WhatsApp Status to post promotional contents about their businesses. This finding is in line with a study by Olanrewaju et al. (2020) which revealed that many youth entrepreneurs in Lagos increasingly use WhatsApp Status to advertise products, promote sales, and build customer loyalty, owing to its direct reach, cost-effectiveness, and familiar interface. This finding supports the views of Obiora and Uche (2021) and Obiora and Uche (2023) which opine that traders in Anambra State and Southeast Nigeria use WhatsApp most for their businesses in post COVID-19 era which enhanced its growth. This shows that Nigerian youths and students overwhelmingly use WhatsApp particularly Status for sales visibility, customer engagement, and cost-effective digital marketing.**

Identifying the types of business promotional content shared on WhatsApp Status by COOU *studentpreneurs* in objective two. It was found that more than half of the respondents post varieties of promotional content on their WhatsApp Status which include; product photos or videos, customer testimonials, product reviews, discounts and offers, behind-the-scenes or production process, order instructions and delivery updates and giveaways and contests contents. This finding shows that there are various types of content young entrepreneurs can share on WhatsApp Status to help expand their customer base and maximize sales. The above finding is in tandem with the finding of Adebayo (2024), which found that entrepreneurs used WhatsApp Status to post a variety of promotional content including: Discount announcements, product demo videos, customer reviews, giveaway campaigns, "How it is made" behind-the-scenes content. It is also in support of and Ezeaka's (2024) stance that WhatsApp Status with the presence of Meta AI can afford a visual and time-bound platform for creative promotions including offers, contests, and real-time feedback.

In Objective three, which **assess the factors influencing the usage of WhatsApp Status for business promotion by COOU *studentpreneurs*. It was deduced that there are several factors that influence *studentpreneurs'* usage of WhatsApp Status for business promotional contents such as** free to use, reaching personal contacts directly, easy to post

updates, real-time feedback from viewers, save cost compared to paid ads and building trust with known customers. The above listed influences are also advantages that come with the usage of WhatsApp app for promotional contents. This finding underpins the scholars' argument for WhatsApp usage (Koledafe, 2024; Mustapha & Ajede, 2024), who in their works have listed the various reasons WhatsApp users find it easy to use.

Furthermore, this study established a relationship between WhatsApp Status usage for business promotion by *studentpreneurs* and the outcome of business patronages experienced by the student entrepreneurs. This supports the theoretical framework of this study, Katz, Blumler and Gurevitch (1973) uses and gratification theory, *which looks at what students use their WhatsApp Status for and the gratification they derive while using this social media app feature*. In this case, COOU *studentpreneurs* utilise WhatsApp Status to fulfill needs related to business visibility, customer interaction, marketing convenience, and economic sustainability and they get gratification of business patronage while they use it. *COOU studentpreneurs find WhatsApp Status appealing for its cost-saving and personalised communication, especially within social circles. The above finding justifies the uses and gratification theory,*

Conclusion

In conclusion, WhatsApp Status serves not only as a personal communication tool but also as a strategic and impactful business promotion medium for student entrepreneurs. Given its widespread usage and functionality. The study revealed several **factors that influence the use of WhatsApp Status for promotional purposes**, including the platform's cost-effectiveness, ability to directly reach personal contacts, ease of use, real-time feedback features, and the trust built through peer-to-peer interactions. These factors underscore why WhatsApp Status stands out as a preferred tool for student-level digital entrepreneurship. This reflects a growing trend among young entrepreneurs who leverage accessible digital platforms to enhance business visibility, drive engagement, and reach potential customers within their social networks.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the effective use of WhatsApp Status as a strategic business promotion tool among student entrepreneurs at Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University:

1. The university, through its entrepreneurship development programme, should integrate digital marketing modules that focus on social media platform like WhatsApp. This will equip *studentpreneurs* with practical

- skills on how to optimise WhatsApp Status for professional business promotion, content creation, and customer engagement.
2. Students who have recorded measurable success through the use of WhatsApp Status should be encouraged to share their experiences with others through seminars, social media groups, or university publications. This peer-sharing strategy can motivate other students to adopt the platform more strategically.
 3. Student-led entrepreneurial clubs and the university's entrepreneurship center should partner with digital marketing experts to host regular workshops on branding, storytelling, and creative content development tailored to WhatsApp and similar platforms. This will improve the quality and professionalism of sales content shared by *studentpreneurs*.
 4. *Studentpreneurs* should be encouraged to monitor their WhatsApp Status views, feedback, and responses in order to improve promotional strategies. Simple tools like WhatsApp's built-in status viewer count and customer response tracking can help evaluate promotional effectiveness.
 5. The university can pilot initiatives that allow students to promote university-registered microenterprises through institutional WhatsApp groups or promotional Status accounts. This will not only boost student businesses but also institutionalize entrepreneurial culture within the university.

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Authors' Contributions

Paschal Agbachukwu initiated the idea of this paper and wrote the first draft with major inputs by Adanma Obiora; and both coordinated the data gathering. Adanma Obiora did the proofreading, and reworked the paper based on the comments from the reviewers.

Declaration of Conflict of Interest

There was no conflict of interest with any sources or persons from the beginning of this paper to the end of it.

Ethical clearance

The authors kindly sought and duly got ethical clearance from the respondents and every other relevant authority who provided the data or information used for this paper.

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